

THE ROLE OF PERSONAL HYGIENE IN THE FORMATION OF HEALTHY LIFE OF STUDENTS

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Annotation. Based on the analysis of scientific and methodological literature and world experience on issues of personal hygiene of the younger generation, the level of health of students of technical specialties at the university is considered. The forms and duration of diseases suffered by students were determined. Based on the study, we can say that the health status of students is deteriorating. One of the ways to solve this issue is to determine ways to improve physical education and health work in the process of physical education of students.

Key words: university students, personal hygiene, healthy lifestyle, maintaining health, physical education and health work.

Introduction. Personal hygiene is considered as one of the most important components of a healthy lifestyle [4, 6, 7]. Knowledge of personal hygiene rules is necessary for everyone. Their strict adherence greatly contributes to the promotion of health and the transfer of psychophysical stress of life and high performance [1, 3].

“Hygiene” (translated from Greek means: “bringing health”, “promoting health”) is one of the sciences about human health, means and methods of preserving and strengthening it [2]. “Personal hygiene” is the observance of the basic principles and rules of this science by each person in the process of his individual life [5]. Along with the term “hygiene”, the term “sanitation” is often used, which translated from Latin means “health”. However, it should be remembered that there are

significant differences in the content of these concepts. Hygiene provides knowledge about health, how to preserve and strengthen it, and sanitation deals with the practical implementation of hygiene requirements and monitoring compliance with the rules established by it [8, 10, 11]. Following the rules of personal hygiene involves, first of all, a rational daily regimen, careful body care, hygiene of clothes and shoes [12, 13, 16, 17].

Compliance with a rational daily regimen is the most important element of personal hygiene, which also reflects its other elements. Compliance with it creates optimal conditions for vigorous activity and effective recovery of the body, and helps to increase mental and physical performance. This is explained by the fact that if the regime is followed, a certain rhythm of the body's functioning is developed, thanks to which a person is able to perform various types of activities with the greatest efficiency [14, 15].

The health benefits of a proper daily routine are due to the fact that the body quickly adapts to relatively constant living conditions. This, in turn, helps to improve the quality of work and study, normal digestion, and improve the quality of sleep, which becomes deeper and more restful [3, 5, 11].

The basis of a rational daily regimen is the correct distribution of time for various types of activities and rest, nutrition and sleep during the day. When establishing a daily regimen, it is necessary to keep in mind that the living conditions of each person are significantly different, and each person is characterized by his own individual characteristics. For these reasons, it is not advisable to establish a strict and uniform daily regimen for everyone.

The purpose of the article is to determine the meaning of personal hygiene and its role in the formation of a healthy lifestyle of a student, as well as to develop pedagogical conditions for its improvement in physical exercise classes.

The basic hygienic provisions in the daily routine of any person can and should be uniform and unshakable. These primarily include the following provisions:

- performing various types of activities at strictly defined times;

- correct alternation of work, educational activities and rest;
- regular meals at the same hours;
- regular exercise;
- useful leisure time, good sleep.

The daily routine of students is established taking into account the age of the students, their individual characteristics, as well as the characteristics of the conditions in which they live and study. When compiling it and especially implementing it, it is necessary to keep in mind that in addition to the very positive effect already noted above on health, physical development and performance, constant adherence to the regime has great educational value. Its observance is especially important in the development of willpower and self-education.

For this reason, a rational daily routine should not be perceived as something imposed from the outside, but as a deeply conscious, personally necessary condition for normal daily activity. For this, it is very important that each student himself takes an active part in its preparation and monitoring its compliance, while being guided by the above-mentioned unshakable requirements. Based on these requirements, as well as taking into account individual characteristics and specific living conditions, an exact daily routine must be drawn up for each student, indicating the start and end times of all main routine moments.

Knowledge and adherence to the rules of personal hygiene is necessary for every person, but it is especially important for those involved in active physical education and sports activities. Their strict implementation helps to increase the effectiveness of educational, training and recreational activities, contributes to the preservation and strengthening of health, and the formation of cultural behavior skills. The development of such rules is carried out by a special direction of hygienic science - hygiene of physical exercises.

The main objective of this direction is to study the influence of various environmental factors on those involved in physical exercises. Based on the data obtained in research, hygienic rules and standards are developed, activities are

organized aimed at improving health, increasing the performance of athletes and athletes, as well as creating optimal conditions for the most effective process of physical education and sports training.

The results of research conducted within the framework of this scientific direction and practical experience made it possible to formulate the following basic sanitary and hygienic requirements, the fulfillment of which is necessary when organizing physical exercise classes:

- hygienically acceptable condition of the places where classes are organized;
- availability of necessary, serviceable and specially prepared equipment and sports equipment;
- compliance by students with personal hygiene rules;
- compliance of weather conditions with basic hygienic requirements (air temperature, humidity, wind, precipitation);
- taking into account the environmental situation in the area where physical exercises take place (inadmissibility of conducting classes near landfills, wastewater treatment plants, environmentally hazardous industries);
- availability of special sportswear and footwear for those involved in the activities;
- taking water treatments after physical exercise.

Physical exercise can only be done in specially designated areas. You cannot exercise in dusty areas or near contaminated areas. Special physical education and sports premises should always be clean and well ventilated. The floors in them should be wiped with damp cloths after each lesson. The temperature in such rooms must meet hygienic requirements. It is extremely important to observe the rules of personal hygiene before, during and after classes.

You should come to classes or competitions with a well-washed body and feet. Particularly strict requirements in this regard are imposed when organizing martial arts and swimming classes.

In gyms you should exercise in shorts and T-shirts. In this form, it is most convenient to practice outdoors under favorable weather conditions and a

temperature of at least 17 degrees. In cool weather, you must wear a tracksuit. For winter sports, special clothing and shoes must be used. Both summer and winter special sports shoes must be worn over socks: in summer it is desirable that they are simple, cotton, and in winter - woolen.

Sportswear and shoes must always be kept clean and tidy. They need to be washed and cleaned regularly, much more often than everyday clothes and shoes. They should only be worn for physical exercise and competition. It is unacceptable to use sportswear and shoes as casual wear. You can exercise only on working sports equipment, sports equipment, using working sports equipment. The size of sports equipment, equipment, accessories, as well as their weight must correspond to the height, age, and individual capabilities of those involved. All students must take an active part in the repair of sports equipment and equipment, creating conditions for its storage in a clean, tidy form, both in a higher educational institution and especially at home.

Conclusions. One of the priority tasks of the physical education system is to develop in students the knowledge and skills of personal hygiene and a meaningful attitude towards maintaining their health. At this time, the number of effective information and methodological systems aimed at developing the foundations of a healthy lifestyle and their use in the system of physical education of students is very small and requires further scientific development.

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